

Judicial Activism in India: Limitations and Policy

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Abstract

Judicial Activism, is the role of an activist played by the judiciary in a nutshell, we can say that judicial activism mean when the judiciary crosses the boundaries or the limits of the power assigned to it by the constitution and goes to the extent of even making laws for correct justice i.e. fair and impartial justice which is the work of legislature i.e. the other organ of government. In this Article the author shall analyze the judgments passed by the Supreme Court evidencing Judicial Activism, and whether the Supreme Court in such cases has 'expanded' its judicial functions beyond its mandate, thus blurring the concept of separation of powers enshrined in the Indian Constitution.

Keywords: Judicial Activism, Judiciary Indian Constitution, Supreme Court

Introduction

The expression 'Judicial Activism' signifies the anxiety of courts to find out appropriate remedy to the aggrieved by formulating a new rule to settle the conflicting questions in the event of lawlessness or uncertain laws. The Judicial Activism in India can be witnessed with reference to the review power of the Supreme Court under Article 32 and Article 226 of the Constitution particularly in Public Interest Litigation. In India, almost all laws have originated from the English Common Law. In England in the absence of existing rules for relief in certain cases and predictive procedure, the Court of equity look the initiative to draw up new rules. The formulation of those new rules by the courts had arisen in certain cases was denoted as Judicial Activism.

Judicial Activism in India

In India Judicial Activism is not a new concept although its intensity has increased over the years. Judicial Activism flows from the power of judicial review which means the power of the courts to pronounce upon the constitutional validity of the acts of public authorities both executive and legislative. This power has been derived by the judiciary through various procedures. The doctrine of separation of power, which was propounded by Jurist Montesquieu, has been adopted in India as the three organs of Government. However this principle in India is not absolute but partial. As stated earlier, the Judicial Activism in India can be witnessed with reference to the review power of the Supreme Court under Article 32 particularly in Public Interest Litigation. For instance the principle of "ABSOLUTE LIABILITY" was propounded in Oleum Gas Leak case, Public Trust Doctrine in Kamalnath case etc. The 42nd Amendment 1976 was undertaken with a view to remove the difficulties created by Judicial Activism. One of the main objectives of 42nd Amendment Act was to establish Parliamentary Supremacy beyond doubt by restricting the scope of the judicial review. But in *Minerva Mills* case 1980 Supreme Court declared that the constitution had conferred only a limited amending power under Article 368 of the Parliament and therefore, it cannot enlarge it into an absolute power.

Judicial Activism Methods

There are various methods of judicial activism that are followed in India. They are:

1. Judicial review (power of the judiciary to interpret the constitution and to declare any such law or order of the legislature and executive void, if it finds them in conflict with the Constitution)
2. PIL (The person filing the petition must not have any personal interest in the litigation, this petition is accepted by the court only if there is an interest of large public involved; the aggrieved party does not file the petition.
3. Constitutional interpretation
4. Access of international statute for ensuring constitutional rights.

5. Supervisory power of the higher courts on the lower courts.

Significance of Judicial Activism

- It is an effective tool for upholding citizens' rights and implementing constitutional principles when the executive and legislature fails to do so.
- Citizens have the judiciary as the last hope for protecting their rights when all other doors are closed. The Indian judiciary has been considered as the guardian and protector of the Indian Constitution.
- There are provisions in the Constitution itself for the judiciary to adopt a proactive role. Article 13 read with Articles 32 and 226 of the Constitution provides the power of judicial review to the higher judiciary to declare any executive, legislative or administrative action void if it is contravention with Constitution.

Judicial Activism Examples

It all started when the Allahabad High Court rejected the candidature of Indira Gandhi in 1973.

In 1979, the Supreme Court of India ruled that under trials in Bihar had already served time for more period than they would have, had they been convicted.

- **Golaknath case** – The questions, in this case, were whether the amendment is a law; and whether Fundamental Rights can be amended or not. SC contented that Fundamental Rights are not amenable to the Parliamentary restriction as stated in Article 13 and that to amend the Fundamental rights a new Constituent Assembly would be required. Also stated that Article 368 gives the procedure to amend the Constitution but does not confer on Parliament the Power
- **Kesavananda Bharati Case** – This judgment defined the basic structure of the Constitution. The SC held that although no part of the Constitution, including Fundamental Rights, was beyond the Parliament's amending power, the "basic structure of the Constitution could not be abrogated even by a constitutional amendment." This is the basis in Indian law in which the judiciary can strike down an amendment passed by Parliament that is in conflict with the basic structure of Constitution.
- In the 2G scam, the SC cancelled 122 telecom licenses and spectrum allocated to 8 telecom companies on the grounds that the process of allocation was flawed.
- The Supreme Court rolled out a blanket ban on firecrackers in the Delhi – NCR area with certain exceptions in 2018.

Relation Between Public Interest Litigation and Judicial Activism in India

Public Interest Litigation or Social Interest Litigation today has great significance and drew the attention of all concerned. Public Interest Litigation is the exception of traditional rule "Locus standi", that a person whose right is infringed alone can file a petition, has been considerably relaxed by Supreme Court in its recent decisions. In other words we can say that judicial activism was made possible in India through the system of Public Interest Litigation (PIL) the legal doctrine "justerti" implying that none except the affected person can approach a court for legal remedy for holding both respect of private and public law application until it was over through by the PIL move. In the beginning the application of PIL was confined only to improving the disadvantaged sections of the society but after the 25th amendment act of 1971 by which primacy was accorded to a limited extent to the directive principles vis-a-vis the Fundamental Rights making the former enforceable rights the expectation of the public soared high and it demanded the courts to improve the administration by giving appropriate directions for ensuring compliance with statutory and constitutional prescription have increased encroaching green belts and open spaces for maintaining ecological balance, forbidding stone crushing activities near residential complexes, earmarking a part of the reserved forest for advasis to ensure their habitat and means of livelihood, compelling the municipal authorities to perform their statutory obligations for protecting the health of community, compelling the industrial units to set up effluent treatment plants, directing installation of Air Pollution, directing closure of hazardous factory in order to save the community from the hazards environmental pollution are some of later significant cases displaying judicial activism.

Problems Regarding the Exercise of Judicial Activism Through Public Interest Litigation

Judicial Activism in Democratic Country like India does not seem to be well for the democratic process in India. Not only in India but also in many other democracies the central point of controversy or conflict is the power of "Judicial Review". The Parliamentary legislation being reviewed and successfully challenged in the HC and SC

has indeed robbed the Indian Parliament of its authority and prestige so much so that it even become impossible to talk of “parliamentary sovereignty” in India which is having a parliamentary form of Government.

Therefore, the critics often argue that judicial review or judicial activism is the counter force in India. The judicial activism of law courts tends to ignore the political capacity of the people to govern themselves. In other words, the dark side is slowly moving to overshadow the bright side of the PIL project.

The limitation regarding the exercise of Judicial Activism through PIL is as follows –

1. **Ulterior Purpose** – Desai and Murlidhar confirm the perception by writing that, “PIL is being misused by people agitating for private grievances in the grab of public interest and seeking publicity rather than exposing public causes.
2. **Inefficient use of limited judicial resources** – Number of judges in much lower in Indian Courts than the number of pending cases. The fact is that courts need years to settle cases might also suggest that probably courts were not the most appropriate forum to deal with the issues in hand as PIL.
3. **Judicial Populism** – Prof. M.P. Jain cautions against such tendency, “PIL is a weapon which must be used with great care and circumspection, the court need to keep in view that under the guise of redressing a public grievance PIL does not encroach upon the sphere reserved by the constitution to the executive and the legislative.”
4. **Symbolic Justice** – Another major problem with PIL in India has been of PIL cases often doing only symbolic justice. So the PIL project might dupe disadvantaged sections of society in believing that justice has been done to them, but without making a real difference to their situation.
5. **Disturbing the Constitutional Balance of Power** – It is rightly said by Porf. M.P. Jain – “PIL is a weapon which must be used with great care and circumspection.
6. **Overuse-induced non-seriousness** – The overuse of PIL dilute the original commitment to use this remedy only for enforcing human rights of the victimized and the disadvantaged group.

Suggestions

Major steps need to be taken in order to prevent an “over-activist” judiciary from transgressing its limits. Some of these can be explained as follows: Public interest litigation, or PIL as it is conveniently called, has become a major and prominent segment of the jurisdiction of the Supreme Court and 21 High Courts in India. Whilst its necessity and utility in upholding the rule of law in undoubted, its extravagant and unprincipled use at times by courts has brought PIL into Controversy.

(1) Relaxation must be procedural

Much of the misapplication of the PIL jurisdiction can be avoided, if it is remembered that PIL is basically the application of the well settled principles of judicial review by courts of government and public authorities, with the modification of courts allowing the petitioner(s) applicant to approach the court on behalf of other persons, who themselves are unable to come to the court because of ignorance of their rights or the difficulty and cost of litigation. In such cases, the court relaxes the strict rule of locus standi of the applicant and also relaxes procedural formalities. It may even entertain a letter addressed to the court by a complainant. PIL was devised as a means for redressing the basic rights of generally the poor and marginalized sections of the society, who were unable to get judicial help on their own. It must also be borne in mind that public interest litigation is not something unique to India. Other jurisdictions such as South Africa, Canada and USA also have public interest litigation, though it is not described as such. It is, therefore, important to note that except for procedural relaxations, the PIL jurisdiction should not exceed the permissible limits and parameters of judicial review by the court over the actions or omissions of government, legislatures or public bodies, or transcend the basic separation of powers underlying the Constitution. Judicial review in a democratic constitution must also not supplant the normal processes of representative self-government, in which the representatives of the people make choices and policies which may not be ideal or correct, but which can be set right by the people themselves. What is not within the bounds of judicial review by courts cannot be within their reach because it comes under the description of public interest litigation before it. PIL jurisdiction is, therefore, not a unique jurisdiction by which courts can transcend their limitations to act as a body to set right actions of the

government, which are believed to be wrong or could be improved. Once this basic foundation of PIL is kept in mind, the parameters of intervention in PIL are easily grasped and its misapplication can be seen and avoided.

(2) Judicial Activism not PIL

Another misconception is equating PIL with judicial activism in India. Judicial activism is not PIL. A court can be judicially active or inactive irrespective of PIL. Judicial activism is a word of many shades. No person today subscribes to Bacon's view that judges must only declare the law and do not make law. Such a view was rightly described as a fairy tale by a distinguished English judge Lord Reid. Judges do and must make law but not in the manner of legislatures. There is much scope for creative judicial activism in the interpretative functions of judges, on the choices inherent in their function and in the gaps in legal rules, as has been done by superior courts in several countries for many years. The Indian Supreme Court's own creative jurisprudence of the inviolability of the basic structure of the Constitution in 1973 and the importation of non-arbitrariness in the fundamental Right of Equality, and of due process of law in the right to personal liberty in Maneka Gandhi's case in 1978, are stellar examples of how judicial function can be creative. Regrettably, this kind of creative judicial activism in Indian courts seems to have become dormant and displaced by a poor substitute of routine judicial correction and monitoring of governmental functions by courts in PIL. Judicial activism is equated with PIL mainly because it is a most convenient vehicle for bringing public grievances before courts and because the courts' orders in PIL are far-reaching and sometimes sensational. Once these fundamentals of judicial review are borne in mind by courts in exercising PIL jurisdiction, it can be a useful judicial process for the benefit of the public, particularly of the poor, the indigent and marginalized sections of society, whose fundamental rights are to be protected by court orders. It is the historic and constitutional duty of courts to safeguard and enforce the basic liberties and rights of individuals. A court is strongest and least vulnerable, when it grounds its interventions in enforcing the basic rights of individuals against authority. No question of the court breaching the separation of powers can arise, as it carries out its constitutional function of protecting the basic rights of individual in such cases.

(3) Judicial activism not Judicial Adventurism

The origins of PIL were in such unexceptional interventions in 1970, as when the court ordered the release of bonded labourers and stopped inhuman working conditions in stone quarries and in mental asylums etc. Correctly, this jurisdiction should have been named SAL or SOCIAL ACTION LITIGATION to gather its true import. It is also the court's legitimate function to enforce the law, not of each and every infraction, but in those cases where its disregard has grave consequences to the public. No question of the court overreaching its powers can arise in such cases. In matters relating to environment, where irreversible damage may be done unless the actions of the authorities are immediately corrected, the court may take prompt corrective measures, but not take over the administration itself or supplant the law. However, over the years, the true objective of PIL as originally conceived has been lost sight of, and it believed to be general jurisdiction for correcting government action or inaction, regardless of constraints of established principles of judicial review. As the court cannot disregard the law in judicial review or disregard the fundamental separation of powers underlying the Constitution to appropriate executive or legislative powers, PIL orders cannot disregard law; take over the administration by government or by public authorities, in the name of improving governance or preventing misuse of power. It is this aspect of misplaced judicial activism, which a bench of two judges of the Supreme Court in Aravalli Golf Club case recently criticized in rather strong words of reprimand. The judgment was timely and has brought misplaced judicial activism into focus, but in the process it did not advert to the permissible scope of judicial intervention.

(4) Displacing Government Administration

It is true that there is a misconception not only in the public but also in courts about the function of judiciary under the Constitution, particularly when PIL is employed. It appears that the public has developed a syndrome of routine recourse to the courts for every perceived failure of government and the courts on their part have come to believe that it is their judicial duty to intervene in such failures by making orders for correcting or improving the government. There is a vast catalogue of such micro-managing orders made by the Supreme Court itself, which cannot be justified by any principle of judicial review. They include orders for making roads in hilly areas, wearing of helmets and seat belts to avoid accidents in cities, cleanliness in housing colonies, disposal of garbage, control of traffic, control of unmanned railway crossings, prevention of pollution of rivers, action plans to control and prevent menace of monkeys in cities, control of breeding of animals in zoos,

measures to prevent ragging of students, collection and storage of blood in blood banks, control of noise and banning of fire crackers. At times, committees set up and empowered by courts have effectively displaced government's administration in those areas. Such PIL petitions are filed in the Supreme Court in its original jurisdiction under the Article 32 of the Constitution. Article 32 is for enforcing fundamental rights. It is hard to find any genuine enforcement of any fundamental right in such PIL petitions. The petitions make a formal invocation of Article 14 in its liberal interpretation of non-arbitrariness or of Article 21 in its vast expanse of a right to life. Article 32 seems to have lost its meaning for all practical purposes.

At times, matters beyond the judicial sphere and competence of the court have been entertained. In 1993, the Supreme Court even ordered that provision of food of 1200 calorific value should be supplied to hostages in an ongoing military operation in Kashmir. The court has professed to monitor a highly technical engineering scheme of interlinking of rivers in India and of genetic modified foods. In the field of higher education, the court's interventions have created a maze of complex regulations by successive cases, familiar only to lawyers, and baffling to educationists, parents and students. The court's scheme for admissions in private medical colleges in the Unnikrishnan case in 1993, which was indistinguishable from legislation, prevailed for nine years before it suffered an inglorious end, when the court itself struck it down as "unconstitutional" in T.M.A. Pai's case in 2002, causing considerable confusion in admissions in professional colleges. Following upon the Aravalli Golf Club case, a larger Bench of the Supreme Court is shortly to consider the parameters of PIL. This is not new. Way back in 1983, a Bench of the court had made reference to a larger Bench, but nothing came of it. If the fundamental premise of public interest litigation (or more appropriately, social action litigation), coupled with the premise that PIL cannot go beyond the limitations of judicial review and must give due recognition to the separation of powers under the Constitution, is borne in mind, a formulation of the instances where PIL may or may not be used, seems unnecessary. It may even be counterproductive, as it is never good to distill judicial power by enumeration. For such matters, Justice Oliver Wendell Holmes once said, "We need to have education in the obvious".

Conclusion

Finally, after examining carefully all these points, it must be said that the scales are tilted in favour of the 'Parliamentary Supremacy'! In India such an arrangement is in conformity with the democratic norms of the country where by the people elect their representatives and gave authority to take decisions for them. In the end one need to remember that India is a democratic country and democracy can never be based on merit solely on whose basis judges are selected rather it is based on emotions, feelings, that can be found only in the elected representatives of people in India.

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